

YEAR ONE REPORT

Growth-based Quantitative Sequencing (GROQ-seq) Platform

2024 updates for GROQ-seq include:

- Started onboarding **6 new protein functions**; 7th queued for 2025
- Shared protocols and tools openly via **Protocols.io**
- Refined assay pipeline for **faster, more reproducible** onboarding
- Expanded data collection to **The DAMP Lab (Boston)** and **NIST (DC)**

Contributors

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About the Align Foundation

The Align Foundation advances predictive modeling in biology by creating reproducible, open biological datasets through global collaboration and automation. Founded in 2021, Align develops experimental platforms and coordinates large-scale data generation across academic and automation partners. Its end-to-end process includes community roadmapping, protocol standardization, reproducible data collection, and benchmarking predictive models. Align's mission is to create a world where biological data is more reproducible, scalable, and shareable. Learn more at alignbio.org and follow us on [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), and [BlueSky](#).

Technical Status Updates

Over the past year, we have engineered the GROQ-seq pipeline to accommodate a wide range of protein functions. The platform can integrate nearly any protein or system that links function to growth—for example, any function with an established directed evolution circuit. The diversity of functions onboarded in the platform’s first year highlights its broad applicability.

The seven functions selected for onboarding in year one include:

- Transcription factors⁷
- Proteases⁶
- Aminoacyl tRNA synthetases⁸
- T7 RNA polymerases⁵
- Histidine kinases⁹
- Single-Chain antibody fragments¹⁰
- Dihydrofolate reductases¹¹

While onboarding timelines may vary based on circuit complexity and prior development, each function follows a standardized pipeline comprising five key stages of methods development (Fig. 1):

Plasmid Design

The high-level plasmid architecture is designed to connect protein function to cell growth.

Initial Circuit Response

The finalized gene circuit is tested for responsiveness to high- and low-functional signals. Functionality is assessed using gene variants or inducer concentrations to determine readiness for optimization.

Circuit Optimization

The circuit’s dynamic range is refined by adjusting RBS and promoter strengths or fine-tuning inducer concentrations. Optimization ensures responsiveness across a broad range of functional levels.

Calibration Ladder Development

Calibration variants spanning the dynamic range are selected by engineering diverse function variants or modulating inducer concentrations. Each variant is barcoded and incorporated into pooled assays.

Assay Validation

Pooled calibration variants are tested in the GROQ-seq platform and compared against singleplex measurements. Strong correlation between pooled and singleplex results confirms assay robustness and readiness for running variant libraries alongside calibration controls.

What Has Not Changed

Our motivation

Throughout the first year of development, our efforts have been guided by a central goal: to create a standardized platform for generating large-scale, ML-ready sequence-to-function datasets. We remain convinced that producing reproducible, scalable, and shareable data is the most effective path toward this objective. The updates described in this report have not altered that mission; rather, every improvement has contributed to optimizing the pipeline. With these enhancements, we aim to bridge the data gap and develop a generalizable predictive model capable of determining any protein function from its sequence.

Open collaboration and knowledge sharing

In its first year, The Align Foundation has openly shared the progress and methodologies of the GROQ-seq initiative. To support the development of new assays and facilitate pipeline adoption across multiple sites, we published the initial GROQ-Seq proposal¹—a step-by-step guide for onboarding new assays, covering plasmid design, circuit optimization, library construction, and data analysis. All protocols have been continuously updated and made available on Protocols.io, a public platform for sharing scientific protocols.

To further enhance accessibility, we established an Open Publishing Pipeline that standardizes and disseminates function-specific proposal documents for each newly onboarded assay. These publications encourage open dialogue about function-space exploration and provide a roadmap for integrating new protein functions into the GROQ-seq framework. Once developed, function-specific protocols are also uploaded to Protocols.io to facilitate onboarding at automation sites.

To strengthen reproducibility, we started development on custom quality control and data analysis procedures, as outlined in the initial proposal. A key aspect of this effort is the development of a reusable data analysis pipeline for deriving quantitative function insights from sequencing data. These tools will be open-sourced, providing both the broader scientific community and our collaborators with a robust framework for analyzing and expanding GROQ-seq datasets.

Using barcode sequencing to measure protein fitness

To generate the scale of data required for predictive modeling, we continue to leverage DNA barcodes alongside the increasingly cost-effective sequencing. This approach enables the measurement of 100,000 to 500,000 variants per assay by analyzing massively pooled variant libraries. Through a cloning process, we actively control barcode diversity to maximize data quality during sequencing.

For rationally designed libraries, where each sequence holds in-

trinsic value, we ensure that each variant is represented by at least three distinct barcodes. This strategy enhances our ability to capture rare and biologically significant effects, such as epistasis and mutation interactions. To achieve this high barcode diversity, we remain committed to the split-barcode strategy outlined in our original proposal¹, in which barcodes are cloned into plasmids in two separate steps to maximize diversity.

Collaborating with NIST

The Align Foundation's collaboration with NIST's Living Measurement Systems Foundry (LMSF)², led by David Ross, has been instrumental in the development of the GROQ-seq pipeline. From ideation to implementation, the LMSF team has played a key role in shaping and refining the pipeline. Building on prior work³ and subsequent collaboration with Simon d'Oelsnitz⁴, the NIST team worked closely with Align to adapt protocols and workflows, culminating in the original GROQ-seq pipeline publication¹. Their contributions—spanning circuit design, assay onboarding, and data analysis—have been central to the success of the pipeline's first year.

During this period, the LMSF team continued its collaboration with d'Oelsnitz to develop the GROQ-seq transcription factor assay, demonstrating a four-decade dynamic range in measuring the LacI, VanR, and RamR transcription factors. Beyond this milestone, they have been pivotal in onboarding five additional protein function assays into the GROQ-seq pipeline. Currently, the LMSF team remains deeply involved at every stage, serving as assay optimization experts, high-throughput automation partners, and leaders in technical knowledge transfer.

The N=2 approach to data collection

Building a generalizable sequence-to-function prediction model requires an enormous amount of data. Achieving this at scale demands multiple automation sites and a "divide-and-conquer" approach. However, data generated across different sites—or even within the same site—must meet rigorous reproducibility standards to yield meaningful biological insights. This principle is embedded in the GROQ-seq project through what we call the N=2 approach. A key objective is to develop a robust pipeline with adaptable methods that can be implemented across diverse facilities with varying automation capabilities.

To test the reproducibility of the GROQ-seq pipeline outside of NIST's LMSF group, we partnered with the DAMP Lab at Boston University to evaluate the N=2 approach in an automated setting, starting with the transcription factor assay. By onboarding the GROQ-seq pipeline at DAMP Lab, we are mitigating the risks of single-site dependency while refining our protocols and automation scripts through a structured technology transfer process. These efforts pave the way for future onboarding at an N=3 automation site and beyond.

Living data

Beyond ensuring reproducibility, establishing multiple sites capable of running the GROQ-seq pipeline is essential for the continuous expansion of functional datasets. This approach enriches the functional landscape of each protein, allowing for deeper exploration of sequence-function relationships. We refer to this evolving nature of the project as living data—where datasets are continuously refined and expanded to explore new protein sequences, assess the effects of inducers or inhibitors, and evaluate novel machine learning (ML) techniques.

What has Changed or Adapted

Refining assay onboarding timelines

In 2024, methods development began for six additional protein functions as part of the GROQ-seq platform (Fig. 1)^{5–10}. A seventh function, dihydrofolate reductase¹¹, was proposed and reviewed in December 2024 and is set to begin methods development in Q1 2025.

When initially projecting timelines for the first GROQ-seq assay, we based our estimates on prior work conducted by the LMSF team on a similar pipeline³. Our ambitious goal was to complete assay onboarding—from plasmid design to circuit optimization and calibration control selection—within a single quarter. However, this projection significantly underestimated the complexity of the process. The onboarding of the transcription factor circuit, which was recently completed, ultimately required nearly a full year of development (Fig. 1). A key takeaway from this first year is that foundational investments in plasmid architecture and circuit engineering are already yielding significant benefits. These early design refinements have led to shorter onboarding times for subsequent functions, improved assay dynamic ranges, and greater control over circuit behavior. These improvements position the GROQ-seq platform for increasingly efficient function onboarding in the future, with each iteration refining the process for broader applications.

Decoupling tuning, optimization, and large-scale collection to better leverage NIST's expertise

In our initial GROQ-seq assay measuring transcription factors, the stages of circuit development and tuning through to large-scale data collection were all originally planned to take place at LMSF. However, we have since revised this strategy to better leverage the LMSF team's expertise in circuit optimization while distributing large-scale data collection.

For each function, circuit development occurs at the home institution of the function proposal leaders. In these small-scale experiments, function proposal leaders serve as plasmid circuit design experts. Once an initial circuit response is measured and preliminary calibration variants are identified, the function

To support this continuous evolution, we remain committed to making GROQ-seq function assays publicly accessible. Our goal is to enable external contributions and facilitate requests to analyze novel libraries of gene variants and experimental conditions, ensuring the long-term adaptability and impact of the GROQ-seq platform.

proposal leaders collaborate with the LMSF team at NIST to refine both circuit function and measurement components. This approach enables LMSF to act as a centralized hub for circuit optimization, supporting multiple function proposal leaders simultaneously while maximizing the efficiency of their laboratory automation resources.

To further expand the LMSF team's capacity to focus on optimizing additional incoming protein functions, we have decided to transition developed GROQ-seq assays to automation partners like the DAMP Lab for large-scale data collection. This distributed model not only mitigates single-site facility risks but also increases throughput while maintaining a robust and scalable platform for functional dataset expansion. Once an assay is fully optimized and calibration controls are established, the workflow proceeds as follows:

Initial Pilot Library Measurement

The NIST team conducts an initial measurement of a pilot library (~100,000 variants).

Transition to Large-Scale Data Collection at DAMP Lab

The finalized assay is transferred to the DAMP Lab for large-scale, continuous experimental runs, enabling the generation of living datasets.

Updating our engineering strategy

We recently published a technical report¹² summarizing key updates from our first year of engineering. All changes from our original strategy were made to accelerate circuit tuning, improve standardization across sites, and enhance data quality. The technical report outlines the following changes:

- Use of dihydrofolate reductase for growth-coupled circuits
- Use of commercially manufactured media
- Defining default sub-library designs for pilot-scale measurements
- Modular plasmid design
- Tuning using inducers rather than constitutive elements
- Accounting for *E. coli* strain restriction and modification effects

What Remains to be Established

Navigating the protein function archipelago

The initial functions onboarded onto the GROQ-seq platform were selected based on prior circuit development and strong collaborator engagement. However, future onboarding will follow a strategic roadmap designed to efficiently explore functional relationships. Our objective is to systematically map the functional landscape rather than iteratively generate datasets for every possible protein. This approach is intended to accelerate the transition from task-specific models to a generalized model for protein function prediction.

The first step in developing this strategy was to define “function” and conceptualize the functional landscape. A key outcome of our Fall 2023 Function Ideation Workshop (London, UK) was the visualization of protein function as an archipelago of functional islands (Fig. 2). Each major function island (Fig. 2A) consists of smaller sub-function islands (Fig. 2B), which are further composed of protein families demonstrating those specific sub-functions (Fig. 2C). For example, the broad functional island of binders includes various binding sub-functions, such as protein-protein and protein-DNA interactions. Zooming in further, the protein-DNA binding sub-island consists of multiple protein families, such as TetR and LacI.

With this functional archipelago framework established, we have structured our data collection strategy accordingly. By collecting data on a specific protein family within a sub-function, we can first develop task-specific models for that family (Fig. 2C1). Leveraging transfer learning, we can then refine models for closely related protein families (Fig. 2C2). By iteratively expanding our datasets and applying transfer learning, we aim to build a general model at the sub-functional level—for example, a model for protein-DNA binding prediction. Once robust models exist at the sub-functional level, we plan to extend transfer learning across sub-functions (Fig. 2B3-4) and ultimately between major function islands (Fig. 2A5-6). At this stage, we envision a general predictive model capable of analyzing any protein sequence and determining its function across the entire protein landscape.

There still work to be done in defining the roadmap for prioritizing functions and protein families, ensuring they are mapped in an optimal sequence to efficiently achieve our goal. We still need to test our theory that this iterative approach to transfer learning is the most efficient path toward developing a generalizable model for protein function prediction. While we can create potential roadmaps for prioritizing functions based on the overlapping functional qualities of known proteins, the latter requires our initial datasets to be created, to be useful for creating task-specific models, and then to be expanded to include closely related protein family targets.

Figure 2: Viewing the protein function landscape as an archipelago. A) Large functional islands are composed of B) small sub-function islands, which are in turn composed of C) protein families that perform that function. Our data collection and transfer learning strategy is shown iteratively, as data is collected on one protein family (1) to enhance the model of a similar family (2) leading to a better model of the sub-function (3) that can be used to better understand a related sub-function (4). This strategy is applied to the highest level, eventually using one function (5) to enhance the model of another (6), until a general model of function can be created.

Usefulness of data for predictive models of protein function

A major goal of GROQ-seq is to generate data that is valuable for training predictive models of protein function. However, the best way to gather valuable data remains an open question. In early 2025, we are gathering data from our pilot library for transcription factors. Upon completing the pilot, we expect to gain initial insights into assay capacity—estimated at 300,000 to 500,000 variants per run—along with large-scale data quality and key scientific questions addressed by each sublibrary. Specifically, the pilot includes:

- A random multi-mutagenesis library to explore each transcription factor’s global epistasis manifold.
- A site-saturation library targeting the three positions at which each transcription factor contacts the operator DNA, providing insights into specific TF-DNA interactions (i.e., operator specificity).
- A comprehensive single-mutation library covering all possible single-amino acid substitutions, insertions, and deletions for each transcription factor, allowing us to analyze individual mutation effects.

By collecting this pilot dataset and using its findings to inform larger datasets, we aim to assess the true utility of the data:

- Is the data sufficient for predictive modeling?
- How can we optimize library design to better explore sequence space?
- Is there a point where adding more data becomes inefficient or redundant?

As we scale datasets across different functional domains, we will continuously refine our library strategies—both for zero-shot and supervised learning approaches—and establish empirical guidelines on the amount of data needed for predictive power (data-scaling laws).

Requesting New Data for Existing Function Assays

To streamline access to finalized GROQ-seq function assays, we are developing a Request Data portal for scientific collaborators. Once an assay is fully onboarded to the GROQ-seq platform, researchers will be able to submit requests to generate additional data by providing a short proposal outlining their scientific objectives and corresponding library design.

If selected, The Align Foundation will:

- Fund the synthesis and cloning of the requested library
- Cover experimental costs
- Host the resulting dataset

Collaborators will have exclusive access to the dataset under a one-year embargo before it is made publicly available.

Function assay extensibility

While collecting new data using an established assay is straightforward, our goal is to continuously expand each GROQ-seq assay to include new protein targets. We have partially tested the idea of extending a developed assay by adding VanR to the transcription factor assay after the gene circuit was optimized. This showed us that for the transcription factor assay, if a new TF’s expression can be tuned to fit the dynamic range of the existing assay, it can use the same gene circuit. We have outlined the levels of development required for expanding an existing assay to new proteins, using the TF assay as an example:

Examples of new TF datasets that could be immediately measured by the GROQ-seq platform:

- Additional LacI, VanR, RamR variants
- Testing a panel of ligands against these existing TFs
- Anything with the same DNA target sequence as the above TFs

Examples that would require some development to be tested in our platform:

- If the TF is not LacI, VanR, or RamR and is not native to MG1655
- The assay is currently optimized for the MG1655LacI knockout (KO) strain, so this would require optimizing the expression of the new TF to match the current assay’s dynamic range

Example of TFs that would need extensive development to be tested in the GROQ-seq platform:

- A TF that is native to MG1655 (a KO strain would need to be built)
- A TF that hasn’t been tested in a biosensor plasmid (i.e., no one has tested a circuit for the TF in vivo yet)

While these examples are true for the TF GROQ-seq assay, the requirements to onboard new proteins to an existing functional assay are function-dependent. We are currently performing user-studies to determine the ideal pathway for new collaborators to use and extend the capabilities of our GROQ-seq function assays.

Data hosting

We are currently developing a web-based data sharing platform to facilitate hosting and sharing of GROQ-seq datasets and metadata. This data platform will allow private and restricted access to generated data during the one-year embargo period and make the data publicly available afterward. This is a critical part of our data-sharing infrastructure and central to the success of

Conclusion

The first year of GROQ-seq development has laid a strong foundation for large-scale, reproducible sequence-to-function data collection. Key takeaways include the need for extended onboarding timelines, distributed assay development, and standardized data-sharing practices. Looking ahead, we will focus on expanding functional assays, refining predictive modeling strategies, and ensuring seamless data accessibility.

Suggested Reading

Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence – function datasets at scale

February 2024, [Zenodo](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1252164)

This publication provides a deep-dive on the GROQ-seq platform and a step-by-step overview of the new function onboarding process.

GROQ-seq Technical Status Report – January 2025

May 2025, [Zenodo](https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.28963640)

This publication gives the status of each GROQ-seq function assay after the first year of development.

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